

Composition and Stability of Lanthanum(III) *p*-nitrobenzene-azochromotropic Acid (Chromotrope 2B) Chelate in Solution

Satendra P. Sangal, Suresh C. Srivastava*, and Arun K. Dey

A detailed study of the composition and stability of lanthanum(III) *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (chromotrope 2B) chelate has been made spectrophotometrically. The chelate is reddish violet in colour (λ_{max} at 540m μ). The composition, as determined by different methods, is 1:1 (metal: chelating agent). The chelate is stable between pH 5.0 and 12.5. The values of log *K*, as determined by two different methods, are 4.5 ± 0.1 and 4.9 ± 0.18 respectively at 25° and at pH 6.0.

p-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (chromotrope 2B, abbreviated in this paper as CTB) is well known for its chromogenic properties. Banerji and Dey¹ and Srivastava and Dey² investigated the composition and stability of the chelate between thorium and chromotrope 2B; Sangal and Dey³ used this reagent as a chelatochromic indicator in complexometric determination of thorium. It has now been observed that chromotrope 2B also forms coloured chelates with scandium, yttrium, lanthanum, and the rare earths. This communication describes the studies on lanthanum-chromotrope 2B chelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

A weighed quantity of lanthanum oxide (Johnson & Matthey), dissolved in HCl (conc.), was estimated by the usual method and the solution was suitably diluted. An aqueous stock solution of *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (B.D.H. reagent) was prepared in doubly distilled water.

Measurements of absorbance were carried out with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, using matched glass cells (1 cm) as described earlier¹. pH measurements were made with a Leeds and Northrup direct reading pH indicator.

Procedure.—Three different methods, viz., (i) the method of continued variation⁴, (ii) the mole-ratio method⁵, and (iii) the slope-ratio method⁶, were used to establish the composition.

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, Louisiana State University, New Orleans, La., U.S.A.

1. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 139.

2. Unpublished.

3. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1961, **183**, 178.

4. *Job, Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

5. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

6. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4486.

Evaluation of the Stability Constant.—The stability constant was obtained by the method of Mukherji and Dey⁷, based on a consideration of the composition of two or more mixtures having the same value of absorbance. The value of the stability constant was also obtained separately by the mole-ratio method⁸.

DISCUSSION

As reported by Srivastava *et al.*⁹, the reagent behaved as a colloidal electrolyte and therefore very dilute solutions of the order of 10^{-4} *M* were used in these investigations. Colour formation was immediate and the absorbance values remained constant for at least 72 hours. All the mixtures were, however, kept for one hour to attain equilibrium.

Nature of Complexes Formed.—The method of Vesburgh *et al.*⁹ was followed. Mixtures containing lanthanum chloride and chromotrope 2B in different stoichiometric ratios, viz., 0:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, etc., were prepared and their absorbance was measured at suitable wave length intervals. The results show that the reagent has its $\lambda_{\max}$ at 515 μ , whereas in all the mixtures the region of maximum absorption shifts to 540 μ , indicating formation of only one chelate having $\lambda_{\max}$ at 540 μ under the conditions of study.

FIG. 1. Absorption of equimolecular solutions at 590 μ ($p=1$; $pH\ 6.0 \pm 0.2$).
Curve A: $c=4.0 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*.
Curve B: $c=2.0 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*.
Curve C: $c=13.3 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*.

FIG. 2. The slope-ratio method ($pH\ 5.0 \pm 0.2$).
Concentration of excess component = 4.00×10^{-4} *M*.
A: 580 μ . B: 590 μ .
10 ml of 4.0×10^{-4} *M* excess component + x ml of 1.33×10^{-4} *M* variable component + $(10-x)$ ml H_2O .

7. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.

8. Unpublished.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—Table I summarises the results on the composition of the chelate, using the continued variations method. In the legends c represents the concentration of lanthanum chloride and p , the ratio c'/c , c' being the concentration of chromotrope 2B. A few of the observations are represented graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE I
Total volume=50 ml. $p=1.0$.

Fig. No.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4 M.$	$\lambda.$	Volume of UO_2SO_4 at peak.	Composition of chelate [La(III): CTB]
1	A	4.00	580m μ	25.0 ml	1 : 1
	B	2.00	580	25.0	1 : 1
	C	1.33	580	25.0	1 : 1
1a*	A	4.00	590	25.0	1 : 1
	B	2.00	590	25.0	1 : 1
	C	1.33	590	25.0	1 : 1
1b*	A	1.00	580	33.33	1 : 1
	B	2.00	580	16.67	1 : 1
1c*	A	1.00	590	33.33	1 : 1
	B	2.00	590	16.67	1 : 1

* Figs. omitted to economise space.

This composition is further corroborated by the results of mole-ratio method (Fig. 3) and slope-ratio method (Fig. 2) and is found to be 1:1.

FIG. 3. Absorbance studies by the mole-ratio method at 590 m μ (pH 6.0 $\pm$ 0.2).
A: $c=2.50 \times 10^{-4} M.$ B: $c=1.25 \times 10^{-4} M.$

Effect of pH on the Stability of the Chelate.—Several mixtures of lanthanum-CTB in the ratio of 1:1 were prepared and their absorbance measured at different pH values. The results show that the chelate is stable between pH 5.0 and 12.5 and the λ_{max} remains at 450m μ in this range.

Calculation of the Stability Constant.—Table II records the values of $\log K$ at pH 6.0 ± 0.2 and at 25° , determined by two different methods. The values obtained by the two methods are in close conformity.

TABLE II

	pH.	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.).
Method of Dey <i>et al.</i>	6.0	4.5 ± 0.10	-6.3 ± 0.2
Mole-ratio method	6.0	4.9 ± 0.15	-6.8 ± 0.2

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

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